

A LIGHT PURSUIT OF INTERTEXTUALITY

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Abstract: this article deals with intertextuality and its forms, reflecting the attitudes towards them along with the views of different authors. The role of intertextuality in the scientific style is considered significant and, despite being studied by a number of scientists, has not yet lost its relevance.

Keywords: intertextuality, paratextuality, metatextuality, plagiarism, reference.

Introduction

The most significant effort in creating a typology of intertextual relations was made by the French linguist J. Jenet's works and in German-language literature, M. Featured in the pfisters ' (1985).

Thus, based on his special term "transtextuality" to mean a holistic intertextual relationship, J. Jenet distinguishes five types of intertextual relationships: 1) intertextuality, as the direct coexistence of two or more texts, for example: quotation, hint, plagiarism; 2) paratextuality, the relationship between the text and its title, preface, letter, epigraph, etc.; 3) metatextuality, that is, the appeal of one text to another predtextual in a comment, criticism and evaluation tone; 4) hypertextuality, if one text-the textual element does not participate — imitation, adaptation, parody, transvestite, and 5) architextuality, typological interaction of Bitty class / type texts [1, p.16-17; 2, p.46].

It is important to admit that such a hierarchy primarily reflects cases of the subjugation of intertextual (or "transtextual", in author terminology) relations. In most variants, species can intersect with each other. For example, according to Jenet, criticism as a form of intertextuality can apply to both the type of architecture and the type of metatextuality. The quote also reflects both intertextuality and hypertextuality.

In works of linguistic orientation, a number of concepts are used in the expression of intertextual phenomena: intertexts, metatextic formations, secondary representation of content, secondary texts, etc. Phenomena related to this text are actively studied by the Basic Law of the development of lison and thinking. This lison and thought presupposes "the accumulation of knowledge and the acquisition of new knowledge on their basis"[3, p.43].

The first criterion — referentiality-the stronger the relationship between texts, the more one text subjects the other and reveals its uniqueness. In this

sense, the next text becomes a metatext for the previous text, but not in chronological content, but in semiotic content. The second criterion of communicativity indicates the degree of understanding of the intertextual link given by the author and the recipient, its degree of focus on the goal. The third criterion – autoreflectivity – will be closely related to the previous ones. This suggests that the author not only consciously and clearly defines intertextual references, but also pays special attention to the metacommunicative aspect, meaning the intertextual input on another text is interrelated. In addition, the fourth criterion — pretexts-determines to what extent there will be a structural foundation for a new whole text.

For the various forms of intertextuality that represent a fragment of knowledge, the altered / fixed nature of the acquisition is of considerable importance [4, p.51]. In other words, it is to formulate alien speech precisely as a matter of expressing oneself / in another form.

Selectivity or selectivity as a fifth criterion determines the degree of accuracy and sampling of the acquisition in a new context, its ability to act as a pars pro toto. Finally, the final sixth criterion, dialogicity, is to determine the new contextualization nature of the assimilated passage, the recipient must determine the degree of dissimilarity or assimilation bshlish with the new context [1, s.26-29]. M. Pfister believes that this model of intertextuality can be expressed as a system of concentric circles. Its center determines the maximum level of intertextuality, the level of intertextuality begins to decrease as it moves away from the center.

So, let's consider the quote based on its state of intertextuality. A separate quote in a way according to the criterion of referentiality reveals to some extent the intertextual intensity, since in some cases it refers to its main work, the intensity of which is not structurally significant. If we consider a quote from the point of view of communicativeness, autoreflectivity and dialogue, then it acquires great intertextual value, especially if one specific and voluminous quote can convey the main content or content aspect of an entire work, which can be important selectivity.

Conclusion

An important aspect of modern world linguistics at the moment is the interaction and assimilation of scientific information, which in its place goes in a way related to different areas of human activity [5].

Another form of intertextuality — plagiarism, for example, is defined as weak intertextuality according to the criteria of referentiality and communicativity, since the author not only does not define, but tries in every possible way to hide the interconnection of his text with the original source. However, in terms of structuralism, plagiarism, on the contrary, acquires a strong intertextuality, such as parodies, imitations and transvestites.

Together with the corresponding quality parameters, they determine the total intensity of intertextuality on the example of a particular text.

The purpose and function of the scientific method is to accurately present, generalize and classify the information and facts that must be conveyed to the reader, advance the idea, keltribe logical arguments, formulate laws [6]. We must add that the relevance of certain criteria of intertextuality for specific cases of text creation and interaction must be determined, since not all of them have the same qualitative expression in different types of communication, for example, in artistic and scientific communication. This corresponds to the idea of intertextuality as a graduated, prototypical phenomenon.

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